

Special Relativity, Conservation Laws and Particle-Wave Duality Part 2

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The expression for total kinetic energy in a single particle bound quantum system is: $\sum_p P(p) \frac{p^2}{2m}$ ((1)) with $P(p) = a(p)^* a(p)$ where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. First of all, ((1)) uses the exact Newtonian nonrelativistic expression for kinetic energy i.e. $\frac{p^2}{2m}$. We suggest this is no surprise because we have argued in previous notes that the quantum free particle $\exp(ipx)$ form follows from special relativity which also yields expressions for p and E . The second feature of ((1)) is that it seems to be consistent with a Newtonian nonrelativistic particle stochastically changing its kinetic energy/momentum magnitude based on a $P(p)$ probability scheme, presumably in time. The third thing we note is that the range of p is larger than allowable p values which appear in $\frac{p(x)p(x)}{2m} + V(x) = E$. $\frac{p(x)p(x)}{2m}$ is a Newtonian expression, but it is possible to have $KE(x) = \frac{\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) \exp(ipx)}{\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)}$ ((2)) = $\frac{p(x)p(x)}{2m}$.

We argue that this is an interesting result, because unlike the $p(x)$ expression which is directly linked to a $v(x)$, $KE(x)$ is only linked with a $v_{rms}(x)$ which does not need to describe motion in space-time accurately because it is $\langle vv \rangle$ which is key for KE_{ave} . Thus, $KE(x) + V(x) = E$ has the form of a Newtonian conservation of energy equation (within the classical turning points), but there is no $v(x)$ describing accurate motion through $x-t$. We note that KE is created using $\exp(ipx)$'s and is completely dependent on $V(x)$ for the $a(p)$ values. (We will discuss how the $KE(x) + V(x) = E$ equation goes beyond Newtonian mechanics at the usual turning points.) The $\exp(ipx)$'s also create an average $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ which shows a probability scheme similar to a 2-slit result and one must use $W^*(x)W(x)$ to find the spatial probability, which presumably is linked to the probability of interaction with the particle in space- x and so may be linked to time spent for interaction. Thus, a $KE(x)$, which is Newtonian within the turning points, is multiplied not by $dx/v_{rms}(x)$, but by $W^*(x)W(x)$ which is then integrated over dx to obtain ((1)). In other words, just like the case of $\exp(ipx)$, where a base kinetic energy $\frac{p^2}{2m}$ applies to the interacting system, $KE_{ave}(x) = \frac{p(x)p(x)}{2m} = ((2))$ within the turning points (which is representative of a classical result for all energy levels) is linked with the overall interaction $W(x)$ through $W^*(x)W(x)$ or a combination of particle and wave (probability) results. This integral then shows the stochasticity present in ((1)).

Stochasticity of a Single Particle Bound System

We first wish to argue that a single particle quantum system, according to the rules of quantum mechanics, seems to be stochastic. In particular, one has the well-known result:

$$KE_{total} = \sum_p P(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \quad (\text{nonrelativistic case}) \quad ((1))$$

Here $\frac{p^2}{2m}$ is the exact kinetic energy of a nonrelativistic Newtonian particle. $P(p)$ seems to suggest that this is the probability for $\frac{p^2}{2m}$ to appear and so KE_{total} is a kind of stochastic average in time, it seems. We note that the range of p is over all p values and not the ones which appear in the classical equation:

$$p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((3))$$

We also note that one could obtain a time probability for the classical bound case of:

$$Dt C1 = P(p) = C dx/|v(x)| \quad ((4)) \quad C1, C \text{ are constants}$$

Then, an equation analogous to ((1)) would be:

$$\text{Integral } dx \quad p(x)p(x)/2m \quad C dx/|v(x)| \quad ((5))$$

We suggest that something curious occurs in the quantum single particle bound case, namely that:

$$p(x)p(x)/2m = KEave(x) \text{ quantum, but } C1 dt \text{ is note } Cdx/|v(x)| \text{ but rather: } W^*(x)W(x)dx$$

(within classical turning points)

$$\text{Here: } W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p)\exp(ipx) \text{ and } KEave(x) = \{\text{Sum over } p \quad a(p)pp/2m \exp(ipx)\} / \{\text{Sum over } p \quad a(p)\exp(ipx)\} \quad ((6))$$

There is still a classical base to average kinetic energy (within classical turning points), but $v_{rms}(x)$ does not carry accurate physical information and cannot be used to determine "dt" which seems to be represented by $W^*(x)W(x)dx$, i.e. the modulus of the interaction probability wave.

In order to try to understand this result, we wish to go back to the roots of $\exp(ipx)$.

$\exp(ipx)$ and Special Relativity

Special relativity, applied to a particle with rest mass, m_0 , yields specific expressions for energy and momentum, namely (in 1-D):

$$E = m_0cc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad \text{and} \quad p = m_0v / \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{In the } v \ll c \text{ limit these yield: } E = m_0cc + .5m_0vv \text{ and } p = m_0v \quad ((8))$$

In general, this is as far as one goes beyond writing some Lorentz invariants. We have suggested, however, that the presence of c (the same in all frames) in ((7)) implies that reaction based signals are present in a particle with rest mass which is moving. These signals are linked with:

$$-E \delta t + p \delta x = 0 \quad ((9a)) \text{ (just like for a free photon) while } -Et + px = \text{constant not}=0 \quad ((9b))$$

Thus, the full ((7)) values appear in ((9a)) indicating that the signal based interaction involves the full E and p values which become the Newtonian $KE = p^2/2m$ and $p = mv$ in the nonrelativistic case (if one pulls out $m_0 c^2$).

We have argued in previous notes that ((9a)) is equivalent to:

$\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ as well as $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ ((10)) (i.e. free particle quantum mechanics).

We note that in the nonrelativistic case, $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is completely dependent on Newtonian values $E = p^2/2m_0$ and $p = mv$ and represents the effects of a signal used in interaction (as seen in the 2-slit experiment). Furthermore, $\exp(iEt-ipx)\exp(-iEt+ipx) = 1$ shows that there is overall uniformity in x and t as far as the center-of-mass is concerned.

We suggest that based on the 2-slit experiment, even though there is uniformity in motion, there is stochasticity in interaction based on $\exp(ipx)$. If this is the case, we suggest that a single particle bound state must also exhibit this stochasticity as we have argued is present in ((1)). There are, however, some unusual features of ((1)).

Analysis of the Single Particle Quantum Bound State

$\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ seems to follow from special relativity, but this only applies to a free particle. What does one do with a bound state based on a potential $V(x)$?

First of all, for $V(x)$ one has classically:

$$p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((11))$$

For $\exp(ipx)$, the kinetic energy is $p^2/2m$ in the nonrelativistic case and so the underlying ideas of ((7)) or Newtonian mechanics are present even in the signal $\exp(ipx)$ scenario. Thus, at least within classical turning points,

$$p(x)p(x)/2m = KE_{ave}(x) = \text{some kind of quantum expression} \quad ((12))$$

The question then becomes: What is the appropriate quantum expression to use in ((12))?

$\exp(ipx)$ holds for a classical particle and represents its signal interaction (as shown in the 2-slit experiment). If $\exp(ipx)$ represents an interaction with a p momentum in the 2-slit case (which is a kind of potential), then it should also apply to $V(x)$, but $V(x)$ has the ability to change p values. Classically, one has a $p(x)$ value at each x (which is deterministic in terms of an interaction). If $\exp(ipx)$ leads to a stochastic interaction result for $V(x)$ (albeit it in angle as $|p|$ remains constant), one would expect that $\exp(ipx)$ interacting with $V(x)$ should also be stochastic, but involve changes in p values.

Furthermore, the 2-slit experiment involves: $\exp(i p \cdot r_1) + \exp(i p \cdot r_2)$ ((13))

In the $V(x)$ bound case, there is no r_1 vector or r_2 vector because the problem is 1-D, but there are different p values, so one should consider:

$$\exp(ip_1x) + \exp(ip_2x) + \dots \quad ((14))$$

The question then becomes: What p values should apply for each x ? Classically, one has one p value at each x , namely $p(x)$. Quantum mechanically, the $\exp(ipx)$ signal interacts over a distance \hbar/p and the potential may change quite a bit over this region. Thus, one cannot just use the $p(x)$ value at x , but needs to use a range of values. One finally needs to know what this range of p values should be and whether it is somehow x dependent. If that were the case, one would have some determinism and not the full stochasticity of ((1)).

For a classical system, the range is based on allowable $p(x)$ values within the classical turning points. The classical turning points represent points for which the kinetic energy is 0. $\exp(ipx)$, however, has a very large \hbar/p range at this point because it is no longer interacting locally and may pick up energy from a $V(x)$ point far off and move as well. The idea of $KE=0$ at turning points does not seem to apply in the quantum case with the signal interaction $\exp(ipx)$. This in itself is a large departure from classical thinking and suggests that the quantum solution extends beyond classical turning points. Furthermore, the quantum interaction involves $\exp(ipx)$ and so one only requires ((12)) to hold within the classical turning points. This does not seem then to restrict p values to the range of classical $p(x)$ ones as long as one may produce $p(x)p(x)/2m$ at each x within the classical turning points

One may finally propose:

$$KE_{ave}(x) = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx) \} \quad ((15))$$

Given that ((1)) holds and is a stochastic statement, one may wonder how to use $KE(x)$ to obtain an equivalent result. One may note that $KE_{ave}(x) = p(x)p(x)/2m$ within classical turning points, but not outside them. Given that $KE_{ave}(x) = \langle v^2 \rangle$, $v_{rms}(x)$ is a mathematical result which is not necessarily accurately linked to dt through $dx = v_{rms}(x)dt$. In fact, such an approach cannot produce ((1)) if one considers $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ which seems to follow from $\int dx \ W^*(x)W(x) = 1$ i.e.

$$\int dx \ W^*(x)W(x) = 1 \ \rightarrow \ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)^*a(p) = 1 \quad ((16))$$

One would expect these then to be two inter-related probability statements, suggesting that $W^*(x)W(x) = P(x)$ which seems to be consistent with $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$. In other words, it gives some information about the center-of-mass motion even though $\exp(ipx)$ is linked to the signal interaction process. Even though $KE_{ave}(x) = p(x)p(x)/2m$ within classical turning points, one does not have a classical process. Rather, one has the classical $KE_{ave}(x)$ equivalent result within classical turning points multiplied by the signal interaction related term $W^*(x)W(x)$ which is consistent with a viewpoint of a single particle having a stochastic $p^2/2m$ which changes stochastically in time without any information about location. This viewpoint is equivalent to an interference $p^2/2m$ probability wave built on $\exp(ipx)$ linked with an interaction with $V(x)$, i.e.

$$\sum_p a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) + V(x) W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((17))$$

$V(x)W(x)$ shows the probabilistic signal interaction with $V(x)$ (which makes use of the full $p=mv$). Given that one has a constant E everywhere, the overall solution is described by $\exp(-iEt)$ which represent a kind of equilibrium situation, in this case one that is localized in space as opposed to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which is non-localized and directional.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ as arising from special relativity and representing a c-signal interaction scheme based on the full particle E and p values (for a particle with rest mass). We note that $\exp(ipx)$ is used to describe a 2-slit experiment and so should also apply to interactions with a potential, suggesting that one does not have local interactions (in each dx) as in Newtonian mechanics. We suggest that if one considers the overall total kinetic energy for a stochastic system with no regard to position, then one has the expression: $\sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} P(p)$. This represents a kind of average kinetic energy in time and is stochastic.

Physically, if one uses $V(x)$ one must deal with space and a $KE_{ave}(x) = p(x)p(x)/2m$ (classical result) within classical turning points. Given that $\exp(ipx)$ is based on a classical $\frac{p^2}{2m}$ and one uses $\exp(ip \cdot r_1) + \exp(ip \cdot r_2)$ for the 2-slit problem, one would expect a $\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ to hold for the $V(x)$ case. One cannot have classical turning points because $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ is very large for $p \rightarrow 0$ and so there would be interactions. Thus, $W(x)$ extends outside the classical turning points and there is nothing preventing $p > \text{Max } p(x)$, $p(x)$ is the classical momentum within turning points. One may consider $KE_{ave}(x)$ as a kind of kinetic energy probability wave: $\{\sum_p a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx)\} / (W^*W)$, but to obtain $\sum_p P(p) \frac{p^2}{2m}$ one requires a dt value. One cannot use $dt = dx/v_{rms}(x)$ to obtain the a result with $P(p) = a(p)^* a(p)$ which follows from $\int dx W^*(x)W(x) = 1$ $W(x)^*W(x)dx$ seems to behave like a dt in this case instead of an expression using $v_{rms}(x)$. Thus, it is a combination of the particle result $KE_{ave}(x)$ (a kinetic energy wave equivalent to $p(x)p(x)/2m$ within classical turning points) and $W^*(x)W(x)$ (very much based on the signal $\exp(ipx)$) which yields the stochastic result $\sum_p a(p)^* a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m}$ for total kinetic energy.